

Shotberry Phenomenon in Olive Trees (*Olea europaea* L.): A Review

Shvan Ramzi Salih

Horticulture Department, College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences,
University of Sulaimani, Sulaymaniyah, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Fakhraddin Mustafa Hama Salih

Horticulture Department, College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences,
University of Sulaimani, Sulaymaniyah, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Ibrahim Maarooof Noori

Horticulture Department, College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences,
University of Sulaimani, Sulaymaniyah, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Salih, S.R., Salih, F.M.H., & Noori, I.M. (2024). Shotberry Phenomenon in Olive Trees (*Olea europaea* L.): A Review. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 896-907.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).78](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).78)

Abstract:

Shotberry olive fruits are those of small, usually seedless which express quantitative parthenocarpy. They either fall before harvest or when harvested, they will be of a low commercial value. Consequently, the increased occurrence of shotberries has a negative effect on fruit and oil contents and can extremely affect the commercial yield of olive orchards. Researchers have proposed that temperature, low pollen viability, self-pollination, or deprived pollination in general promote shotberry formation in olive trees. It is observed that the onset of parthenocarpic (shotberry)

phenomenon is a growth occurred in olive which is accompanied by the expansion of all four ovules, in contrast to the selection and growth of a single functional ovule in normal fertilized ovaries. However, abnormal ovule development, such as incomplete embryo sac formation, is not appeared to be a cause of shotberry formation. Furthermore, low or high temperatures, depending on the growing region, may play a role in shotberry formation. Besides, self- and cross-pollination alter the ratio of seedless fruit bearing in most varieties, and cross-pollination is known to improve seeded fruit set and reduce the incidence of worthless shotberries. The olive yield produced from shotberries is caused by self-incompatibility and/or inter-incompatibility, which indicates that pollination is insufficient in the olive orchard. Some varieties show different fruit sizes that produced from fertilized flowers and shotberries. It is also clearly observed that the sole spray application of Boron (B) or its combination with nitrogen (N) significantly decrease shotberry fruits and the level of fruit abscission; however, zinc (Zn) may also play a role in decreasing shotberry at a certain concentration. Furthermore, when polyamines (PAs) such as putrescine (Put) were applied at full bloom, they were very effective in decreasing the percentage of olive shotberries and increasing the percentage of normal fruits. This review describes some olive shotberry aspects and reasons.

Keywords: *Olive shotberry, temperature, cross-pollination, fertilizer, polyamines.*

Introduction

The olive is a fruit tree of high economic value and a basis of a healthy food because of the high nutritional value of its products which are mainly table olives and olive oil. Olive farming and production are geographically restricted by temperature, as an important factor (Langgut et al., 2019). Olive tree growth and production are preferred in areas that have moderate cold winters, and a warm and dry weather during fruit maturation; hence, olive cultivation is situated mostly in the Mediterranean climate regions (Mougiou et al., 2020). Olive is the most important oil-producing tree of the Mediterranean region, including Turkey, Syria, Palestine, and Israel (Diez et al., 2015). Spain is the largest olive producer, with a production of more than 900000 tonnes of olives per annum. In terms of overall world production, Italy and Spain together account for 50%. In the world, 2713.5 thousand tonnes of olive oil are being produced on a commercial scale in 47 countries on five continents (Mansour et al., 2018).

In olive trees, seed formation is important for final fruit growth and continuity during the current year, besides, flower profuseness in the following year (Rapoport, 1993). Stutte and Martin (1986a) proposed a compulsory role for embryo existence in fruit formation up to about 6–8 weeks after flowering. Furthermore, the impact of embryo existence on fruit survival until the time of harvest is not clear because large amounts of fruits may come to maturity without containing an alive embryo (Lavee et al., 1996). It could be seen that the existence of the seed in the fruit affects flowering in the following year. It was noticed that branches of cultivars (cvs.) ‘Manzanillo’ and ‘Koroneiki’ bearing fruit whose seed had been destroyed bloomed the following spring, but the varieties that are bearing seeded fruit did not bloom (Stutte and Martin, 1986b).

Shotberry olives fruits are those of small, usually seedless which express quantitative parthenocarpy. They either fall before harvest or when harvested, they will be of a low commercial value. Accordingly, an increased occurrence of shotberries will have a negative effect on fruit

crop and produced oil, and these can extremely affect the economic yield of the orchards. The size of shotberries, compared to normal fruit, was related to decreased accumulation of photosynthates, while the seed absence was anticipated to play a crucial role in this fruit abnormality phenomena (Márquez et al., 1989).

Shotberry development appears to be influenced by a sequence of environmental factors. The higher ratio of shotberries was documented in olive orchards grown in areas where the average temperature reached 41 °C during flowering season in comparison with the areas of lower average temperatures during this time (Ayerza and Coates, 2004). Low pollen viability (Lavee et al., 2002), self-pollination (Sibbett et al., 1992), or poor pollination in general (Martin et al., 1994; Cuevas et al., 2001 and Ayerza and Coates, 2004) have been mentioned as factors that promote shotberry formation in olive trees. Ugrinovic and Štampar (1996) noticed that the formation of shotberries was genotype-dependent, for example, the cv. ‘Leccino’ is more prone compared to other cvs. However, no significant effect on final yield was observed. An increased appearance of shotberry was also observed to be repeated in the years of higher fruit loads. The aim of this review is to describe olive shotberry (parthenocarpic) fruit phenomenon with showing some treatments that may have effects to overcome shotberry formation in olives (*Olea europaea* L.).

Olive Shotberry Nature

Olive Flower Pollination and Fertilization in Relation to Shotberry

Perfect and imperfect flowers are there on the olive tree (Navas-López et al., 2017); a rudimentary or absent ovary occurs on the imperfect ones; this is a very prevalent phenomenon of morphological sterility, as well as stamina or masculine gender flowers, which are fruitless (Rapoport, 2014). It is obvious that among the olive inflorescences, many of perfect and imperfect flowers are existed. For example, for four periods marked by flowering: in the first

one, there were 26 flowers per inflorescence, from which 11 of them had unfolded petals. The second period had 23 flowers, among which 10 of them were opened petals. In the third period, 22 flowers, with 9 of unfolded petals were occurred, whereas in the last period, out of 13 born flowers, 11 were open (Ruiz et al., 2019). These data let researchers to decide that the production of inflorescences and flowers has been variable since it is affected by climatic, physiological, and genetic factors (Beghè et al., 2015).

The variability and performance of flowers in the inflorescences and the opening capacity did not exceed 50%, in comparison with those that accomplished growth, pollination and fruit set cycle. Likewise, many of the flowers became parthenocarpic fruits and small drupes with a black colour that did not grow because they were influenced by the temperature, photoperiod, soil water availability, variety and low supply of pollen (because of the discrepancy of flowering) (Ruiz et al., 2019). However inside, although they had seeds, they were fell off 15 to 30 days after fruit set (Carvajal-Rodríguez and García-Molano, 2017). According to Rojo and Pérez-Badia (2014), when environmental factors are adverse, or there is a competition between the different organs of the plants, the premature abscission of fruits or parthenocarpic fruit development can be stimulated, which may have arisen as a result of the trees which had water stress (Ruiz et al., 2019), with rainfall lower than 450.4 mm (Puertas Orozco et al., 2011), which gave rise to a prolonged vegetative recovery and then vegetative growth resumed when enough rainfall did occur.

The olive requires cross-pollination, with spreading the pollen grains over 12 km (Seifi et al., 2015). Moreover, the pollen-pistil self-incompatibility is a property of the pollination on the flowers. Thus, the flower pistil biochemically recognizes and rejects the pollen of the same genotype (Barranco Navero et al., 2017). Also, the olive flower gives pollen after a day of pollen sac dehiscence and continues until 48 hours later; in consequence, the plants have viable pollen until 3 or 4 days after flowering, ensuring that the pollen gets to receptive stigmas

(Zhu et al., 2013). Nevertheless, this circumstance is remained unfamiliar in the region of the study, since there spread productive trees only, without information about the compatibility between pollinating varieties, and the duration and viability of pollen have not been identified.

Ovary of Normal and Shotberry Olives

The impossibility of fertilization and seed development which caused by the lack of embryo sac formation does not cause shotberries in the olive. Although there were many ovules in which the embryo sac did not develop, there were few ovaries with more than two such abnormal ovules. Anatomical observation of shotberry ovules revealed both unformed and developed embryo sacs indicating that other factors determine the formation of those fruits; in other words, shotberry and normal fruit formation are affected by other factors rather than whether or no embryo sacs were developed (Rapoport and Rallo, 1990). Ovule growth in the early stages of parthenocarpic fruit stages development has been observed for many species, including apple (Goldwin, 1985) and watermelon (Sedgley, 1979). These observations in olive flowers support what concluded by Sedgley (1979) that the ovule stimulates ovary development in parthenocarpic as well as normal fruits.

The outset of shotberry development in olive was characterized by the growth of all four ovules, whereas in the developing normal fruits, growth occurred only for the functional ovule. Fertilization of one ovule appears to only arrest further development of the other (abortive) ovules. Many characteristics were similar for the functional and parthenocarpic ovules, including early ovule expansion, vascularization and dense cytoplasmic staining of the inner epidermis of the integument. These similarities suggest the involvement of common developmental factors in the two ovule types in spite of fertilization only of the functional ovule. The cytological changes in the integument are particularly unexpected in the parthenocarpic ovules because those changes appear to be linked with

embryo/endosperm nutrition (Rapoport and Rallo, 1990).

Genetic Aspect of Olive Parthenocarpy

In modern oliviculture, it is essential to implement new cultivars resulted from traditional and/or genetic improvement modern technologies, or from the selection amongst varied genotypes grown in the Mediterranean region, which are estimated to be around 4000 of cultivars and accessions (Bartolini et al., 1998).

Olive shows some tendency to natural parthenocarpy under some environmental conditions, although the fruits remain very small as they do not develop normally. Genes inducing parthenocarpy would permit the development of parthenocarpic fruits with regular size and would overcome the problem related to self-sterility among olive cultivars. Self-sterility is controlled by the placental-ovule-specific Def H9 gene regulator sequence, expressed during early flower development. The introduction of the parthenocarpy gene of *Arabidopsis thaliana* may allow fruit development and subsequently boost the yield, and may help to overcome the pollination problem as already successfully tried in eggplant (Rotino et al., 1997). In addition, the reduction of flower numbers observed in kiwi may contribute to solve the waste of energy and to reduce the alternate bearing (Rugini et al., 1996).

Impact of Temperature on Olive Fruit Set and Shotberry Formation

Initial olive commercialization efforts took place in areas with climates similar to where they originated; however, in the middle of the twentieth century, commercial plantations began in environments varied from the Mediterranean basin. In their early life cycle, these olive cultivars showed problems with fruit set and bearing, plus plant growth and metabolism which were being intensely affected by different environmental conditions found in these regions, compared with the Mediterranean climate (Ayerza and Sibbett, 2001).

The best areas in the Mediterranean olive growing region are those characterized by mild, rainy winters and long, warm, dry summers

(Noggle and Fritz, 1983; Sibbett and Osgood, 1994; Ayerza and Sibbett, 2001; Barranco Navero et al., 2017; Fitter and Hay, 2012; Steward, 2012). Extreme temperatures affect the olive trees' reproductive cycle (Bradle et al., 1961; Griggs et al., 1975; Hartmann, 1953; Lavee, 1996; Tous and Ferguson, 1996). Cross-pollination improves fertilization and fruit set under hot environments, as well as in years of poor flower quality (Cuevas et al., 2001; Ghrisi et al., 1999). The need for cross-pollination exists when air temperatures during olive bloom exceed 30 °C (Barranco Navero et al., 2017). Another problem in warm, dry ecosystems is a very short winter chilling period (Ayerza and Sibbett, 2001). This increases the self-pollination incompatibility for many cvs., but it has no effect on open pollination (Lavee et al., 2002).

During olive flowering, occurrence of high temperatures increases pollen incompatibility, in which pollen tubes of an olive cultivar frequently become blocked between the stigma and embryo sac under these conditions. As air temperatures increase from 26.7 to 32.2 °C, pollen tubes from foreign olive cvs. were found to be more aggressive, so they can reach the embryo sacs before they corrupt (Bradle et al., 1961). Research has demonstrated that the dissemination of olive pollen is most effective within a radius of 30 m of pollinators (Sibbett and Osgood, 1994). However, under hot arid conditions, the distance for effective pollination is reduced (Therios, 2009).

Some researchers mentioned that low temperatures could be an important factor that determines the production of pseudodrupes, also known as "shotberry" (Michailides et al., 2011). Also, Koubouris et al. (2010) described that low air temperature incidents during blooming period amplified shotberry in some olive cultivars. In contrast, Ayerza and Coates (2004) stated that a higher ratio of shotberries was observed in olive trees grown in areas where average temperature reached 41 °C during the flowering period compared to areas of lower temperatures.

Some Measures to Minimize Shotberry Phenomenon in Olives

Cross-Pollination to Reduce Olive Shotberries

Cross-pollination is identified to enhance seeded fruit set and decrease the occurrence of valueless shotberries, and this was elegantly demonstrated by Sibbett et al. (1992) via 'Manzanillo' olive cultivar. Pollen source can affect the formation of normal and shotberry 'Manzanillo' olives (Griggs et al., 1975). Despite 'Manzanillo' is self-compatible, the quantity of seeded fruits raised and the quantity of shotberries decreased as pollen of other olive cultivars fertilized 'Manzanillo' flowers. Pollens from 'Barouni' and 'Sevillano' largely enhanced the formation of seeded 'Manzanillo' fruit and decreased the occurrence of shotberries. Pollen grains of both 'Mission' and 'Ascolano' were less effective, while the flowers of the self-pollinated 'Manzanillo' caused the most frequent shotberries and hence the lowest amounts of seeded fruits. These findings propose that some degree of self-incompatibility may occur in 'Manzanillo' (Sibbett et al., 1992; Wu et al., 2002). Also, they observed that cross-pollination of 'Manzanillo' is advisable to increase production. Although it is self-compatible, 10% of plantings of the orchard should be carried out to a pollinizer cultivar to amend optimal production of seeded 'Manzanillo' fruit and minimize the incidence of valueless parthenocarpic shotberries. Since the fruits of pollinizer cultivars are of considerably less value and more difficult to handle within a 'Manzanillo' planting, less dedication of land for pollination purposes would be favourable. Here, it shows that topical utilization of supplementary olive pollen can be an achievable choice to the devotion of the land to olive pollinizer cultivars within the orchards of 'Manzanillo' cv.

In another study carried out by Koubouris et al. (2010) who investigated the effect of three different pollination treatments (self-, cross-, and free-) on the amount of shotberry production of olive tree cvs. 'Koroneiki', 'Kalamata', 'Amigdalolia' and 'Mastoidis' for three consecutive years. In their study,

controlled crosses were achieved for the cross-pollination treatments, while for the free pollination treatment, flowers were allowed to receive pollens from more than 40 cultivars existed in the orchard. Significant statistical differences were observed between treatments, as well as between cultivars and years. The minimum number of shotberry formation was found in free-pollinated trees, whereas the maximum was noticed in self-pollinated trees of all cultivars. Low air temperature incidents at the time of the flowering period elevated shotberry. Cultivars 'Koroneiki' and 'Mastoidis' were mutually the most effective pollinator varieties in decreasing shotberries. The 'Koroneiki' cultivar could be considered as the most appropriate pollinizer to diminish shotberries in cv. 'Kalamata'. When cv. 'Amigdalolia' was cross pollinated by each of 'Koroneiki' and 'Mastoidis' cv., the degree of shotberry formation was lower when compared to cross-pollination caused by the pollinizer cv. 'Kalamata'.

Furthermore, Mhanna et al. (2015) carried out a study to find out the effect of self-sterility of 'Khodeiri', 'Frantoio' and 'Picholine' cultivars on the formation of commercially worthless fruits "Shotberries" by estimating self-incompatibility and "shotberries" degrees which are formed after self- vs. open-pollination, additionally, anatomical aspects of fruits were studied to evaluate the fertilization statuses. The results established that the pollen presence was enough over 64% for all cultivars. All examined cultivars were undergoing an index of self-incompatibility (ISI) in different degrees (ISI Khodeiri=0.21-0.24, ISI Picholine= 0-0.09, ISI Frantoio= 0.12-0.19). Self-pollination produced a high degree of commercially worthless fruits, "Shot berries", and their degrees increased in the 2014 season because of drought. The anatomical study exhibited that all "Shotberries" had no seed and were formed from unfertilized flowers, which caused an inconsistent development. Shot berries were entirely dropped in advance of harvesting time. The results verified the importance of planting a combination of cultivars in olive groves to improve production and minimize the degree of unwanted commercially worthless fruits.

Additionally, Ayerza and Coates (2004) showed in their study which conducted in two ecosystems with hot and arid condition (Arid Chaco in La Rioja, Argentina and Sonoran Desert in Arizona, USA) to decide whether supplementary pollination of Manzanillo cultivar has the possibility to rise yields and lower the degree of shotberry, and to assess the success of different cultivars as sources of pollen. Branches that gained supplemental pollination gave 21% more olive yields than the control. In Arizona, olive yield and shotberry ratio (unpollinated olive) were meaningfully varied between treatments. Branches that received supplemental pollination gave 98% more olives and had 58% lower shotberries when compared to the branches of the control rows. Substantially, more olives were born on branches pollinated with 'Sevillano' and 'Arbequina' pollen, compared with those pollinated with 'Ascolano' pollen and with the control.

Foliar Application of Fertilizers for Reducing Olive Shotberries

There are various environmental and cultural practices that influence fruit set of olive trees. Nitrogen is considered the most effective factor in this connection (Sibbett and Ferguson, 2005). Urea spray is reported as an ideal carrier of N and has a highly significant impact on olive fruit set increasement (Cimato et al., 1994; Frega et al., 1995). Several other scientists have proved that foliar spray of urea in olive trees stimulates the transformation of N from the leaves to the inflorescences and growing fruits. Therefore, with competition between demanding sinks, fruit set and total yield were increased (Klein and Weinbaum, 1984). The results of several researches have shown that the application of boron (B) in several fruit tree species has increased the fruit set even when the B concentration in leaves was not in a proper level (Shrestha et al., 1987; Hanson, 1991), while in several other fruit tree species, boron application decreased the shotberry fruit percentages (Fregoni et al., 1978; Seidy, 1998). Results of several research works indicate that zinc (Zn) plays a key role in pollination and fertilization of flowers and good fruit set. In this context, Talaie and Taheri (2001) investigated the influence of

foliar application of urea $\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, boric acid H_3BO_3 and zinc sulphate ZnSO_4 each with 0.5% concentration either alone or combinational in Zard olive cultivar; the results demonstrated that urea spray of 0.5% concentration significantly enhanced initial fruit set while spraying with B and Zn resulted in a significant increase of final fruit set and the amount of fruits only in the time of fruit harvest, and in general, due to application of B and Zn sprays, the fruit drop was also reduced. It was also clearly found that sole treatment of B spray or its combination with N significantly reduced shotberry fruits and the degree of fruit abscission. Significant and positive correlations were noticed between the B content of fruits, P content of leaves and fruit set. Meanwhile, there was a significant negative correlation coefficient between fruit N content and the percent shotberries. Similarly, Sayyad-amin et al. (2015) obtained the least percentages of shot berries when they applied 2000 mg.L^{-1} zinc sulphate, 2000 mg.L^{-1} boric acid and 7500 mg.L^{-1} urea, either alone or combinational. In contrast, Spinardi and Bassi (2012) indicated that foliar application of B did not significantly affect shotberry ratio. Furthermore, no trend toward increased or decreased shotberry set was detectable across different B treatments.

Role of Polyamines in Reducing Olive Shotberry

The role of nutrition and polyamines (PAs) are very valuable. Polyamines have been mentioned as modulators of plant development (Galston, 1983), and encouragement of plant growth regulators (PGRs) had been associated with an elevation in their biosynthesis in growing plant tissues (Smith and Davies, 1985; Bagni and Torrigiani, 1992). Precisely, PAs have been connected with embryogenesis, root formation, pollen formation, floral initiation, early fruit development, leaf senescence and stress response (Tiburcio et al., 1990; Rastogi and Davies, 1991). Furthermore, plants exhibiting the altered level of PAs, display abnormal phenotypes that can be retrieved to the wild-type by the utilization of PAs (Kumar et al., 1996). Furthermore, it is evident that fruit development is stimulated by growth regulators (Gillaspy et al., 1993). In peas and tomato, production of

parthenocarpic fruit is induced by gibberellic acid (GA_3). Other plant growth regulators result in changes in the concentration of PAs, and in the expression of genes of PAs biosynthesis (Carbonell and Navarro, 1989; Pérez-Amador et al., 1995). There are results suggesting that PAs may have a role in early fruit development in some species (Costa and Bagni, 1983; Rugini and Mencuccini, 1985; Crisosto et al., 1988; Evans and Malmberg, 1989; Egea-Cortines and Mizrahi, 1991). Variations in PAs content have been associated with fruit growth in the course of the cell division stage of some annual and woody crops, suggesting that PAs biosynthesis is correlated with post-fertilization growth and development of ovary tissues (Slocum and Galston, 1985). In apple fruit tissues (Biasi et al., 1988), avocado fruits (Kushad et al., 1988) and grape berries (Shiozaki et al., 2000), quantities of free polyamines (PAs) are somewhat high during the first weeks following full bloom, and becoming fewer gradually shortly afterwards. Whereas, the role of these variations in the growth and development of fruit and seed still remains uncertain in tomato, a temporary increase in PAs level during early parthenocarpic fruit development was stimulated by GA_3 applied one day in advance of anthesis (Alabadi et al., 1996), and a short-term increase of ornithine decarboxylase and spermidine synthase transcripts in GA_3 -treated ovaries has been also found (Alabadi and Carbonell, 1998).

For olive shotberry, in a study conducted by Bagheri et al. (2017), the effects of sprayed polyamines (PAs), putrescine (Put) and spermidine (Spd) on parthenocarpic fruits (shotberries) and olive fruit set were estimated. Putrescine at 2.5 and 5 mM.L⁻¹ and spermidine at 1.25 and 2.5 mM.L⁻¹ were applied on olive tree (*Olea europaea* L. cv. Fishomi) branches added at full bloom (FB) and two weeks after full bloom (2WAFB). Then the ratio of normal and shotberry fruits were determined. Endogenous quantities of PAs in the mesocarp and seeds were also determined at both times of PAs treatment till fruit maturity. The results revealed that putrescine was very successful in reducing the quantity of the shotberries and elevated the quantity of normal fruits when PAs sprayed at

FB. Mesocarp had the maximum putrescine content in Put at 5 mM.L⁻¹ and Spd at 2.5 mM.L⁻¹ treatments, respectively. In the seed, the highest content of PAs was recorded in putrescine treatment of 5 mM.L⁻¹, and the highest spermidine content was observed in spermidine treatment of 2.5 mM.L⁻¹. At time, in relation to polyamines and olive fruit development, another investigation was done by Pritsa and Voyiatzis (2004) to evaluate the seasonal changes of polyamine contents of vegetative and reproductive olive organs in connection to floral initiation, flowering and fruit development; according to the results, high degrees of both polyamines, free and non-free spermidine and spermine, were quantified in buds and shoot apices in the time of the cold period, especially in "Chondrolia Chalkidikis" olive cultivar, probably correlated to cold-hardiness exhibited by this cultivar. Two peaks of total spermine were observed in the buds, the first is occurring in January–February and the second in mid-April, corresponding with the morphological differentiation of flowers and the inflorescence appearance, respectively. Polyamine degrees in ovaries diminished after ovule fertilization and continued low during the subsequent growth of fruit tissues. Spermidine production, especially in the non-free form, was achieved during mid-August; the period of high physiological activity of embryo and fruit growth, pit hardening, and prior to the second growth flush in early September. The results emphasized a direct connection between the of polyamine fluctuations and the developmental processes of olive fruits.

Conclusion

One of the problems in olive trees is shotberry fruits that is more dependent on plant genetics. In addition to genetic factors, environmental factors and nutrition are important in this case. Productivity in the olive is often reduced by the occurrence of parthenocarpic fruitlets. Shotberry in olive may be determined by the number of ovules that grow or expand; in a normal fertilized ovary, a single ovule grown. Low or high temperature is another factor that

regionally determines shotberry formation. In addition, cross-pollination rather than self-pollination reduces olive shotberry formation, as well as N, B and Zn at certain concentrations, could be positive options to diminish shotberry. Also, polyamines have a role to decrease unwanted olive shotberry phenomenon.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

Alabadi, D. & Carbonell, J., 1998. Expression of ornithine decarboxylase is transiently increased by pollination, 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, and gibberellic acid in tomato ovaries. *Plant Physiology*, 118(1), pp.323-328. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.118.1.323>

Alabadí, D., Aguero, M. S., Pérez-Amador, M. A., & Carbonell, J. (1996). Arginase, arginine decarboxylase, ornithine decarboxylase, and polyamines in tomato ovaries (changes in unpollinated ovaries and parthenocarpic fruits induced by auxin or gibberellin). *Plant Physiology*, 112(3), 1237–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.112.3.1237>

Ayerza, R., & Coates, W. (2004). Supplemental pollination-increasing olive (*Olea europaea*) yields in hot, arid environments. *Experimental Agriculture*, 40(4), 481–491. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479704002133>

Ayerza, R., & Sibbett, G. S. (2001). Thermal adaptability of olive (*Olea europaea* L.) to the Arid Chaco of Argentina. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 84(3), 277–285. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(00\)00236-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(00)00236-4)

Bagheri, S., Abedy, B., Rahemi, M., Nemati, H., & Rowshan, V. (2017). Changes in polyamine levels in relationship to the growth and development of parthenocarpic fruits (shotberries) of olive (*Olea europaea* L.). *Scientia Horticulturae*, 215, 172–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2016.11.034>

Bagni, N., & Torrigiani, P. (1992). Polyamines: A new class of growth substances. In *Progress in Plant Growth Regulation* (pp. 264–275). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-2412-5_24

Barranco Navero, D., Fernández Escobar, R., & Rallo Romero, L. (2017). *The cultivation of the olive tree* (7th ed.). Mundi-Press Books.

Bartolini, G., Prevost, G., Messeri, C., & Carignani, G. (1998). *Olive Germplasm: Cultivars and World-Wide Collections*. FAO.

Beghè, D., Molano, J. F. G., Fabbri, A., & Ganino, T. (2015). Olive biodiversity in Colombia: A molecular study of local germplasm. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 189, 122–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2015.03.022>

Biasi, R., Bagni, N., & Costa, G. (1988). Endogenous polyamines in apple and their relationship to fruit set and fruit growth. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 73(2), 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-3054.1988.tb00598.x>

Bradle, M., Griggs, W., & Hartmann, H. (1961). Studies on self-and cross-pollination of olives under varying temperature conditions. *California Agriculture*, 15(3), 4–5.

Carbonell, J., & Navarro, J. L. (1989). Correlation of spermine levels with ovary senescence and with fruit set and development in *Pisum sativum* L. *Planta*, 178(4), 482–487. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00963758>

Carvajal-Rodríguez, D., & García-Molano, J. (2017). Determination of the floral development of the olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.) under the climatic conditions in Alto Ricaurte-Sutamarchán-Boyacá. Undergraduate thesis, Foundation Juan de Castellanos University, Tunja, Colombia.

Cimato, A., Sani, G., Marzi, L., & Marranci, M. (1994). Olive crop efficiency and quality: Effect of foliar fertilization with urea. *Olivae*, 54, 48–55.

Costa, G., & Bagni, N. (1983). Effects of polyamines on fruit-set of apple. *HortScience*, 18(1), 59–61.

- Crisosto, C. H., Lombard, P. B., Sugar, D., & Polito, V. S. (1988). Putrescine influences ovule senescence, fertilization time, and fruit set in 'Comice' pear. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 113(5), 708–712. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.113.5.708>
- Cuevas, J., Diaz-Hermoso, A. J., Galian, D., Hueso, J. J., Pinillos, V., Prieto, M., Sola, D., & Polito, V. S. (2001). Response to cross-pollination and choice of pollinisers for the olive cultivars (*Olea europaea* L.) 'Manzanilla de Sevilla,' 'Hojiblanca,' and 'Picual.' *Olivae*, 85, 26–32.
- Diez, C. M., Trujillo, I., Martinez-Urdiroz, N., Barranco, D., Rallo, L., Marfil, P., & Gaut, B. S. (2015). Olive domestication and diversification in the Mediterranean Basin. *New Phytologist*, 206(1), 436–447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.13181>
- Egea-Cortines, M., & Mizrahi, Y. (1991). Polyamines in cell division, fruit set and development, and seed germination. In *Biochemistry and Physiology of Polyamines in Plants* (pp. 143–158). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-3336-3_9
- Evans, P. T., & Malmberg, R. L. (1989). Do polyamines have roles in plant development? *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 40(1), 235–269. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.pp.40.060189.001315>
- Fitter, A. H., & Hay, R. K. M. (2012). *Environmental physiology of plants* (3rd ed.). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2010-0-66164-2>
- Frega, N., Garzi, R., Mancuso, S., & Rinaldelli, E. (1995). The effect of foliar nutrition on olive fruit-set and on the quality and yield of oil: Further testing. *Advances in Horticultural Science*, 9(3), 148–152. <http://digital.casalini.it/10.1400/14401>
- Fregoni, M., Scienza, A., & Miravalla, R. (1978). Studies on the role of boron in the floral biology and fruiting of Grapevine. *Societa Orticola Italiana*, 615–622. Cab. Abs.
- Galston, A. W. (1983). Polyamines as modulators of plant development. *Bioscience*, 33(6), 382–388. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1309097>
- Ghrisi, N., Boulouha, B., Benichou, M., & Hilali, S. (1999). Agro-physiological evaluation of the phenomenon of pollen compatibility in olive: Case of the Mediterranean Collection at the Ménera Station, Marrakech. *Olivae*, 79, 51–59.
- Gillaspy, G., Ben-David, H., & Gruissem, W. (1993). Fruits: A developmental perspective. *The Plant Cell*, 5(10), 1439. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.5.10.1439>
- Goldwin, G. K. (1985). The role of ovules in the survival of hormone-induced parthenocarpic apple flowers. In G. P. Chapman, S. H. Mantell, & R. W. Daniels (Eds.), *Experimental Manipulation of Ovule Tissues* (pp. 89–108). Longman.
- Griggs, W. H., Hartmann, H. T., Bradley, M. V., Iwakiri, B. T., & Whisler, J. E. (1975). Olive pollination in California. *Bulletin of the California Agricultural Experiment Station* (869).
- Hanson, E. J. (1991). Sour cherry trees respond to foliar boron applications. *HortScience*, 26(9), 1142–1145.
- Hartmann, H. T. (1953). Effect of winter chilling on fruitfulness and vegetative growth in the olive. *Proceedings of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 62, 184–190.
- Klein, I., & Weinbaum, S. A. (1984). Foliar application of urea to olive: Translocation of urea nitrogen as influenced by sink demand and nitrogen deficiency. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 109(3), 356–360.
- Koubouris, G. C., Metzidakis, I. T., & Vasilakakis, M. D. (2010). Influence of cross-pollination on the development of parthenocarpic olive (*Olea europaea*) fruits (shotberries). *Experimental Agriculture*, 46(1), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479709990679>
- Kumar, A., Taylor, M. A., Arif, S. A. M., & Davies, H. V. (1996). Potato plants expressing antisense and sense S-adenosylmethionine decarboxylase (SAMDC) transgenes show altered levels of polyamines and ethylene: Antisense plants display abnormal phenotypes. *The Plant Journal*, 9(2), 147–158.

<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-313X.1996.09020147.x>

Kushad, M. M., Yelenosky, G., & Knight, R. (1988). Interrelationship of polyamine and ethylene biosynthesis during avocado fruit development and ripening. *Plant Physiology*, 87(2), 463–467. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.87.2.463>

Langgut, D., Cheddadi, R., Carrión, J. S., Cavanagh, M., Colombaroli, D., Eastwood, W. J., Greenberg, R., Litt, T., Mercuri, A. M., Miebach, A., & Roberts, C. N. (2019). The origin and spread of olive cultivation in the Mediterranean Basin: The fossil pollen evidence. *The Holocene*, 29(5), 902–922. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683619826654>

Lavee, S. (1996). Biology and physiology of the olive tree. In *World Olive Encyclopedia* (pp. 61–110). International Olive Council.

Lavee, S., Rallo, L., Rapoport, H. F., & Troncoso, A. (1996). The floral biology of the olive: Effect of flower number, type, and distribution on fruit set. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 66(3–4), 149–158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4238\(95\)00842-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4238(95)00842-1)

Lavee, S., Taryan, J., Levin, J., & Haskal, A. (2002). The significance of cross-pollination for various olive cultivars under irrigated intensive growing conditions. *Olivae*, 91, 25–36.

Mansour, T. G. I., Hassan, H. B. A., Abd El-Ghani, S. S., & Khalil, S. E. M. (2018). The Tunisian experience in olive production and marketing and how to benefit from it in the Egyptian case. *Middle East Journal of Agricultural Research*, 7(3), 1154–1164.

Márquez, J. A., Benloch, M., & Rallo, L. (1989). Seasonal changes of glucose, potassium, and rubidium in ‘Gordal Sevillana’ olive in relation to fruitfulness. *International Symposium on Olive Growing*, 286, 191–194. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1989.286.30>

Martin, G. C., Ferguson, L., & Polito, V. S. (1994). Flowering, pollination, fruiting, alternate bearing and abscission of olive tree. *University of*

California, Division of Agriculture and Natural Resources Publication, 3353, 51–56.

Mhanna, M., Douay, F., & Al-Qaiem, F. (2015). Self-sterility in some olive cultivars and its influence on parthenocarpic fruits ("shot berries") formation. *Syrian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 1(2), 117–128.

Michailides, T. J., Vossen, P. M., & McKenry, M. V. (2011). Diseases of olive in California. In *Olive Diseases and Disorders* (pp. 379–401). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0647-0_19

Mougiou, N., Baalbaki, B., Doupis, G., Kavroulakis, N., Poullos, S., Vlachonassios, K. E., & Koubouris, G. C. (2020). The effect of low temperature on physiological, biochemical and flowering functions of olive tree in relation to genotype. *Sustainability*, 12(23), 10065. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122310065>

Navas-López, J. F., León, L., Rapoport, H. F., Moreno-Álías, I., Medina, M. G., Santos, C., Porrás, R., Lorite, I. J., & de la Rosa, R. (2017). Flowering phenology and flower quality of cultivars ‘Arbequina,’ ‘Koroneiki,’ and ‘Picual’ in different environments of southern Spain. *International Symposium on Flowering, Fruit Set and Alternate Bearing*, 1229, 257–262. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2017.1229.38>

Noggle, G. R., & Fritz, G. J. (1983). *Introductory Plant Physiology* (2nd ed.). Prentice-Hall Inc.

Pérez-Amador, M. A., Carbonell, J., & Granell, A. (1995). Expression of arginine decarboxylase is induced during early fruit development and in young tissues of *Pisum sativum* (L.). *Plant Molecular Biology*, 28(6), 997–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00042098>

Pritsa, T. S., & Voyiatzis, D. G. (2004). Seasonal changes in polyamine content of vegetative and reproductive olive organs in relation to floral initiation, anthesis, and fruit development. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 55(10), 1039–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AR04053>

Puertas Orozco, O. L., Carvajal Escobar, Y., & Quintero Angel, M. (2011). Study of monthly rainfall trends in the upper and middle Cauca

River basin, Colombia. *Dyna*, 78(169), 112–120.
<https://doi.org/10.15446/dyna.v78n169.37810>

Rapoport, H. F. (1993). The timing and developmental context of olive embryo growth. *II International Symposium on Olive Growing*, 356, 268–271.
<https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1994.356.48>

Rapoport, H. F. (2014). The reproductive biology of the olive tree and its relationship to extreme environmental conditions. In *VII International Symposium on Olive Growing*, 1057, 41–50.
<https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2014.1057.2>

Rapoport, H. F., & Rallo, L. (1990). Ovule development in normal and parthenocarpic olive fruits. *Acta Horticulturae*, 286, 223–226.
<https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1990.286.31>

Rastogi, R., & Davies, P. J. (1991). Effects of light and plant growth regulators on polyamine metabolism in higher plants. In *Biochemistry and Physiology of Polyamines in Plants* (pp. 187–199). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-3336-3_11

Rojo, J., & Pérez-Badia, R. (2014). Effects of topography and crown-exposure on olive tree phenology. *Trees*, 28(2), 449–459.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00468-013-0954-5>

Rotino, G. L., Perri, E., Zottini, M., Sommer, H., & Spena, A. (1997). Genetic engineering of parthenocarpic plants. *Nature Biotechnology*, 15(13), 1398–1401.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1297-1398>

Rugini, E., & Mencuccini, M. (1985). Increased yield in the olive with putrescine treatment. *HortScience*, 20(1), 102–103.

Rugini, E., Caricato, G., Muganu, M., Taratufolo, C., Camilli, M., & Camilli, C. (1996). Genetic stability and agronomic evaluation of six-year-old transgenic kiwi plants for rolABC and rolB genes. *III International Symposium on In Vitro Culture and Horticultural Breeding*, 447, 609–610.

<https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1997.447.94>

Ruiz, S., Leonard, O., & Almanza-Merchán, P. J. (2019). Olives and olive oil production in the Alto Ricaurte climate region in Boyaca, Colombia. *Revista Colombiana de Ciencias Hortícolas*, 13(1), 108–119.
<https://doi.org/10.17584/rcch.2019v13i1.9202>

Sayyad-amin, P., Shahsavari, A. R., & Aslmoshtaghi, E. (2015). Study on foliar application nitrogen, boron, and zinc on olive tree. *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, 13(2), 131–136.
<https://doi.org/10.15547/tjs.2015.02.004>

Sedgley, M. (1979). Ovule and seed growth in pollinated and auxin-induced parthenocarpic watermelon fruits. *Annals of Botany*, 43(2), 135–140.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.aob.a085551>

Seidy, M. (1998). The effect of foliar spray with Zn and B on pistachio nut quality and quantity. (PhD Dissertation). University of Tehran, Iran.

Seifi, E., Guerin, J., Kaiser, B., & Sedgley, M. (2015). Flowering and fruit set in olive: A review. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 5(2), 1263–1272.

Shiozaki, S., Ogata, T., & Horiuchi, S. (2000). Endogenous polyamines in the pericarp and seed of the grape berry during development and ripening. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 83(1), 33–41.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4238\(99\)00089-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4238(99)00089-7)

Shrestha, G. K., Thompson, M. M., & Righetti, T. L. (1987). Foliar-applied boron increases fruit set in 'Barcelona' hazelnut. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 112(3), 412–416.

Sibbett, G. S., & Ferguson, L. (2005). *Olive Production Manual* (Vol. 3353). UCANR Publications.

Sibbett, G. S., & Osgood, J. (1994). Site selection and preparation, tree spacing and design, planting, and initial training. *Olive Production Manual*, 3137, 27–34.

Sibbett, G. S., Freeman, M., Ferguson, L., & Polito, V. S. (1992). Effect of topically applied 'Sevillano' pollen on normal-seeded and

parthenocarpic "shotberry" fruit set of 'Manzanillo' olive. *HortTechnology*, 2(2), 228–230. <https://doi.org/10.21273/horttech.2.2.228>

Slocum, R. D., & Galston, A. W. (1985). Changes in polyamine biosynthesis associated with postfertilization growth and development in tobacco ovary tissues. *Plant Physiology*, 79(2), 336–343. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.79.2.336>

Smith, M.A. & Davies, P.J., 1985. Separation and quantitation of polyamines in plant tissue by high performance liquid chromatography of their dansyl derivatives. *Plant Physiology*, 78(1), pp.89-91. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.78.1.89>

Spinardi, A., & Bassi, D. (2012). Olive fertility as affected by cross-pollination and boron. *The Scientific World Journal*, Article ID 375631. <https://doi.org/10.1100/2012/375631>

Steward, F. C. (2012). *Plant Physiology 7A: A Treatise: Physiology of Development: Plants and Their Reproduction* (Vol. 7). Elsevier.

Stutte, G. W., & Martin, G. C. (1986a). Effect of killing the seed on return bloom of olive. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 29(1–2), 107–113.

Stutte, G. W., & Martin, G. C. (1986b). Effect of light intensity and carbohydrate reserves on flowering in olive. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 111(1), 27–31.

Talaie, A., & Taheri, M. (2001). The effect of foliar spray with N, Zn, and B on the fruit set

and cropping of Iranian local olive trees. *Acta Horticulturae*, 564, 337–341. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2001.564.40>

Therios, I. N. (2009). *Olives* (Vol. 18). CABI. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781845934583.0000>

Tiburcio, A. F., Kaur-Sawhney, R., & Galston, A. W. (1990). Polyamine metabolism. In *The Biochemistry of Plants: Intermediary Nitrogen Metabolism* (Vol. 16, pp. 283–317). Academic Press.

Tous, J., & Ferguson, L. (1996). Mediterranean fruits. In J. Janick (Ed.), *Progress in New Crops* (pp. 416–430). ASHS Press.

Ugrinovic, K., & Štampar, F. (1996). Fertilization of olive (*Olea europaea* L.) cultivars 'Istrska Belica,' 'Pendolino,' and 'Leccino' by different pollinators. *Zbornik Biotehniške Fakultete Univerze v Ljubljani, Kmetijstvo*, 67, 183–188.

Wu, S. B., Collins, G., & Sedgley, M. (2002). Sexual compatibility within and between olive cultivars. *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology*, 77(6), 665–673. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14620316.2002.11511563>

Zhu, W., Zhou, P., Xie, J., Zhao, G., & Wei, Z. (2013). Advances in the pollination biology of olive (*Olea europaea* L.). *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 33(2), 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chnaes.2013.01.001>